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Complete response rates in rectal cancer: Temporal changes over a decade in a population-based nationwide cohort

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In the past decade many changes in neoadjuvant treatment for patients with rectal cancer have taken place and are expected to impact complete response rates. The aim of this study was to investigate the impact on pathological, and overall, complete response rates in a nationwide population-based cohort, in relation to changes in neoadjuvant treatment and the start of a Watch & Wait (WoW) study.

Materials and methods: A nationwide register study using prospectively collected data from the Swedish Colorectal Cancer Register between 2009 and 2020. Patients with rectal cancer stage I-III with a ypT0N0 in the resected specimen after neoadjuvant treatment and clinical complete responders from the yearly inclusion data of the national WoW study were included. Temporal changes in pathological and overall complete response rates were analysed, and differences in neoadjuvant treatment regimens over time and per region were studied.

Results: Between 2009 and 2020 the pathological complete response rate for rectal cancer remained similar (Mann-Kendall tau of 0.091, $p = 0.68$) while the overall complete response rate increased significantly from 3.0% to 9.6% (Mann-Kendall tau of 0.818, $p < 0.001$). The pathological complete response rate for patients receiving short course radiotherapy followed by chemotherapy was reduced by 50% after the introduction of the WoW study.

Conclusions: During the studied time period the overall complete response rate increased significantly presumably due to changes in national neoadjuvant treatment regimens. Since the start of the national WoW study clinical complete response seem to partly replace pathological complete response.

1. Introduction

After the introduction of the Total Mesorectal Excision (TME) surgery, treatment and management of rectal cancer has continuously evolved [1]. Over time several randomized trials, partly carried out in Sweden, have suggested changes in neoadjuvant treatment regimens particularly for more advanced rectal cancer [2–4]. At the same time organ preserving strategies have internationally gained more acceptance and are increasingly applied after neoadjuvant treatment [5].

The Stockholm Trials and the Swedish Rectal Cancer Trial paved the way for short course neoadjuvant radiotherapy (SCRT), and the Dutch

TME study confirmed the benefit of neoadjuvant radiotherapy even when performing TME surgery [6–9]. In 2017 the Stockholm III trial reported that SCRT with delayed surgery is safe and reduces post-operative complications [2]. A few years later the RAPIDO trial indicated a benefit of SCRT followed by systemic chemotherapy compared to chemoradiotherapy (CRT) for locally advanced rectal cancer, although data indicated an impaired local control after SCRT and chemotherapy [4]. Many hospitals across Sweden have included patients in these trials and, over time, treatment practices and guidelines have changed, not only in Sweden, but all over Europe.

Pathological complete response (pCR) after neoadjuvant treatment

Abbreviations: WoW study, (Watch & Wait study); pCR, (pathological complete response); cCR, (clinical complete response); SCRCR, (Swedish Colorectal Cancer Registry); SCRT, (Short course radiotherapy); CRT, (chemoradiotherapy).

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in the resected specimen is associated with an excellent prognosis [10]. As a consequence, Habr-Gama's team pioneered the Watch and Wait (W&W) approach and multiple subsequent studies have now indicated the feasibility of omitting surgery in patients with a clinical complete response (cCR) [5,11,12]. The proportions of pCR and cCR reported in clinical trials vary between 10 and 60% and depends on neoadjuvant treatment regimen used and initial tumour stage [4,13–15]. Presumably due to more intensive treatment and a longer interval the chances of achieving a complete response seem highest when radiotherapy and systemic chemotherapy are both delivered prior to surgery (i.e. total neoadjuvant treatment (TNT)) [4,13,14].

Following the increasing acceptance for W&W internationally, a nationwide prospective clinical W&W study was initiated in Sweden in 2017 and W&W is not recommended outside this study (WoW, [clinicaltrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov/NCT03125343) NCT03125343). On a population level, it is reasonable to assume pCR rates decline over time after the introduction of W&W for patients with cCR. However, it remains difficult to identify all patients with a cCR and because of changes in neoadjuvant therapy the overall complete response rates and, thereby potential for W&W in a population, are difficult to predict.

Sweden has a comprehensive national quality register for rectal cancer patients and the on-going national study includes the vast majority of Swedish W&W patients. Using these data, we aimed to assess temporal changes in pathological, and overall, complete response rate in relation to changes in neoadjuvant treatment and the start of the national WoW study.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data sources

This is a nationwide registry-based cohort study. Data on all pCR patients were extracted from the Swedish Colorectal Cancer Registry (SCRCR). The SCRCR is a national registry including all patients treated for rectal cancer and contains comprehensive information on baseline staging, neoadjuvant treatment and follow up. The SCRCR was established in 1995 for rectal cancer and has a completeness of 98.8% [16]. All patients diagnosed with rectal cancer between Jan 1, 2009 and Dec 31, 2020 who were treated with neoadjuvant radiation with or without chemotherapy, underwent surgery (abdominal or transanal) in whom a pCR in the pathological specimen was registered were included. Patients with distant metastases (M1) at diagnosis and patients with positive lymph nodes at pathology (ypN+) even if ypT0 were excluded from this study.

Overall complete response should include both patients with pCR and cCR. However, W&W patients are not comprehensively registered within SCRCR. Before the initiation of the Swedish WoW study non-operative management was highly unusual in Sweden. The study started accrual in 2017 and since W&W is strongly discouraged outside this clinical study it includes most patients with a W&W strategy after neoadjuvant treatment in Sweden.

All background data on the rectal cancer population were retrieved from the publicly accessible website of the SCRCR (<https://statistik.inca.net.se/kolorektal/rektum/>). Data collected include total number of rectal cancer patients receiving neoadjuvant therapy, year and type of neoadjuvant therapy delivered, and region where treatment was delivered. The data for this report was extracted on 17th of November 2022 [17].

This study was approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (Dnr 2021-01741).

2.2. Outcomes

The outcomes of this study were temporal changes in overall complete response rate (pCR combined with cCR), regional differences in pCR rate and differences in pCR rate between neoadjuvant treatment

regimens.

2.3. Definitions

Overall complete response rate was defined as the number of patients with pCR or cCR divided by the total number of neoadjuvant treated patients. A pCR was defined as a ypT0N0 in the resected specimen. According to the protocol of the Swedish WoW study a cCR was defined as such when on MRI, endoscopy and digital rectal examination (DRE) no suspicion of remaining tumour existed. All included patients have undergone MRI including diffusion-weighted images (DWI) and most cases display areas of homogenous fibrosis on MRI without any suspicious lymph nodes. Endoscopy must show a scar and/or telangiectasias.

Neoadjuvant treatment regimens were grouped into five categories: SCRT with immediate surgery (SCRT+immediate surgery), SCRT with a waiting interval (SCRT+delayed surgery), SCRT with a waiting interval with systemic chemotherapy (SCRT+chemotherapy), conventional chemoradiotherapy (CRT), and a group with treatment not in accordance with these regimes defined as "other". In accordance with the definitions used by SCRCR, immediate surgery is defined as surgery within 21 days after the last dose of SCRT. A waiting interval is defined as surgery more than 35 days after the last dose of radiotherapy. SCRT+chemotherapy included both treatment according to the RAPIDO scheme and treatment with only four cycles of capecitabine (as described in the study protocol for the study LARCT-US, [clinicaltrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov/NCT03729687) NCT03729687). In line with the protocol of the Swedish WoW study the national guideline recommends re-assessment 6–8 weeks after CRT or SCRT [18]. When SCRT+chemotherapy is given recommendations are to follow RAPIDO and LARCT-US protocol which state re-assessment 1–2 weeks after the last chemotherapy cycle.

Administratively, Swedish healthcare is divided in six regions with inhabitants ranging between 1 and 2.5 million. Within each region local collaboration and policymaking affect patient management but national guidelines for neoadjuvant treatment have existed through the full study period. However, guidelines have changed over time and implementation differs between regions.

2.4. Data analysis

Baseline characteristics were extracted for all pCR patients. Crude rates were determined for categorical variables and the median including interquartile range (IQR) for continuous variables. The yearly pCR rate was calculated by dividing the total number of patients with a pCR by the total number of patients with neoadjuvant treatment in that year. Starting 2017 and onward, the annual overall complete response rate was calculated by dividing the total number of patients with a pCR or cCR by the total number of patients with neoadjuvant treatment in that year. The presence of a temporal trend was assessed using the Kendall tau (rank correlation) statistics. We divided the study period into two intervals, 2009–2014 and 2015–2020. Differences between these periods regarding pCR rates were calculated with the chi-square test. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 27 (IBM SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL).

3. Results

Between 2009 and 2020 a total of 10 232 patients were registered in the SCRCR as having received neoadjuvant treatment for rectal cancer stage I-III prior to surgery. During this time period 401 patients in Sweden had a pCR in the resected specimen, making the overall pCR rate in this period 3.9%. The median age at diagnosis was 67 years and 166 (41.4%) patients were female. 206 (51.4%) patients had a cT3 tumour at baseline and the majority of patients had lymph node metastases (i.e. cN+). All baseline characteristics and the type of neoadjuvant treatment given for patients with pCR are shown in [Table 1](#). Absolute numbers for pCR and cCR in relation to the total neoadjuvant treated patients for

Table 1
Baseline characteristics for all patients with a pathological complete response.

		All pCR patients (n = 401)	
Gender	male	235 (58.6%)	
	female	166 (41.4%)	
Age at diagnosis (median)		67 (59–73)	
	Baseline T stage in categories	cT1-2	62 (15.5%)
		cT3	206 (51.4%)
		cT4	123 (30.6%)
Baseline N stage in categories	cTx/ missing	10 (2.5%)	
	cN0	102 (25.4%)	
	cN1-2	285 (71.0%)	
Type of treatment	cNx/ missing	14 (3.5%)	
	SCRT + immediate surgery	27 (6.7%)	
Type of surgery	SCRT + delayed surgery	122 (30.4%)	
	SCRT + chemotherapy	72 (17.9%)	
	CRT	180 (44.8%)	
	APR	199 (49.6%)	
Type of surgery	LAR	169 (42.1%)	
	Hartmann	26 (6.5%)	
	TEM	6 (1.5%)	
	Other	1 (0.2%)	

^aData are median (IQR) or n (%).

^bCRT = chemoradiotherapy; CT = chemotherapy; SCRT = short-course radiotherapy; APR = abdominoperineal resection; LAR = low anterior resection; TEM = transanal endoscopic microsurgery.

each year between 2009 and 2020 are shown in [Table 2](#). From 2009 to 2020 a statistically significant increase is observed for the overall complete response rate (Mann-Kendall tau of 0.818, $p < 0.001$) but no significant trend is observed for pCR alone (Mann-Kendall tau of 0.091, $p = 0.68$). Starting in 2017, one patient was included in the Swedish WoW study followed by 25, 36 and 39 patients in the following years (Mann-Kendall tau of 0.759, $p = 0.002$).

The yearly stacked cumulative incidence of the different neoadjuvant treatments is shown in relation to the complete response rates (pCR and cCR) in [Fig. 1](#). Over these 12 years a relative decline is observed in proportion of patients treated with both SCRT+immediate surgery and CRT while an increased rate is observed for SCRT+delayed surgery, SCRT+chemotherapy, and other types of neoadjuvant

Table 2
Yearly pathological and clinical complete response rates between 2009 and 2020.

Year		Pathological (pCR)	Clinical (cCR)	Overall CR
2009	Total	899		
	CR	27 (0.3%)	-	27 (3.0%)
2010	Total	857		
	CR	22 (2.6%)	-	22 (2.6%)
2011	Total	910		
	CR	31 (3.4%)	-	31 (3.4%)
2012	Total	925		
	CR	34 (3.7%)	-	34 (3.7%)
2013	Total	917		
	CR	50 (5.5%)	-	50 (5.5%)
2014	Total	824		
	CR	37 (4.5%)	-	37 (4.5%)
2015	Total	894		
	CR	42 (4.7%)	-	42 (4.7%)
2016	Total	907		
	CR	50 (5.5%)	-	50 (5.5%)
2017	Total	904		
	CR	40 (4.4%)	1 (0%)	41 (4.5%)
2018	Total	812		
	CR	25 (3.1%)	25 (3.1%)	56 (6.2%)
2019	Total	836		
	CR	21 (2.5%)	36 (4.3%)	62 (6.8%)
2020	Total	638		
	CR	22 (3.4%)	39 (6.1%)	64 (9.6%)

^aNumbers are n (%).

treatment.

In the period between 2009 and 2014 13.7% of patients (25/182) receiving SCRT+chemotherapy had a pCR. Between 2015 and 2020 this proportion decreased to 6.9% (47/681, $p < 0.001$). No significant difference in pCR rate was found for the remaining types of neoadjuvant treatments when comparing the two time periods ([Table 3](#)).

In [supplementary Figure 1](#) the yearly stacked cumulative incidence of types of neoadjuvant treatment in each of the six health-care regions is presented. The total pCR rates in the two time periods is shown in [Table 4](#). The pCR rate in the first half of the study period (2009–2014) was highest in region A and region D: 5.8% (76/1319) and 5.3% (53/1005), respectively. In comparison with the four other regions, both these regions have a relatively large proportion of patients receiving SCRT+delayed surgery patients during 2009–2014 and display reduced pCR rates in the second half of the study period (2015–2020). Regions B and E, with apparent treatment strategy changes around 2014–2015, both display statistically significant increases in pCR rates over time ([Appendix 1](#) and [Table 4](#)).

4. Discussion

Between 2009 and 2020, the overall complete response rate tripled for patients with rectal cancer who were treated with neoadjuvant treatment in Sweden. Presumably, this increase was due to implementation of new neoadjuvant regimens. The pCR rate steadily decreased from 2016 onwards and was in part replaced by patients with a cCR. In the first half of the study period the highest pCR rate was observed for patients receiving SCRT+chemotherapy but in this group the pCR rate was reduced by approximately 50% during the second half, the time period when W&W was gradually implemented. Although there may be a few cCR patients not accounted for, it is reasonable to believe that these results reflect the development within a nationwide population over time.

Although the first results from the WoW study will be reported in more depth elsewhere, this is the first study to report on a nationwide overall complete response rate, combining both pathological and clinical complete response. Our study period reflects a time during which significant changes have taken place in rectal cancer management, with shifting neoadjuvant treatment regimens on one hand and inclusion in the WoW study on the other. For all patients receiving neoadjuvant treatment, the pCR rate ranges between 3 and 7% and the reported cCR rate increased every year from 1% in 2017 to 6% in 2020. The start of a national WoW study will presumably have instigated increased awareness of organ saving possibilities and has given hospitals a safe referral pathway to include patients in a WoW study.

From the public data disclosed by the SCRCR it can be concluded that SCRT+delayed surgery is increasing in its use in Sweden, replacing SCRT and immediate surgery. For more advanced tumours SCRT+chemotherapy has almost completely replaced CRT, initially within the setting of clinical trials but from 2021 onwards this strategy is also recommended as standard of care in the Swedish national guideline for rectal cancer^{4 18}. Naturally, a waiting interval after SCRT provides time for tumour regression which, in combination with increasing use of SCRT+chemotherapy, presumably explains the tripling of overall complete response rate on a nationwide level. This finding is also in line with the results from the RAPIDO trial showing a doubled pCR rate with SCRT+chemotherapy compared to CRT [4]. With increasing chances at finding a cCR, mandatory re-assessment after neoadjuvant treatment should have a prominent role in multidisciplinary teams to give patients the opportunity to choose to enter a study with organ preservation.

This study has some limitations. It is a registry-based study that uses multiple data sources which makes it generally impossible to prove causal relationships. However, since multiple randomized controlled trials have reported on significantly higher pCR rates after TNT and longer waiting interval it is reasonable to assume that the gradual increase of TNT and delayed surgery has impacted complete response rates

Fig. 1. Overall complete response rate (both pathological and clinical) in relation to different types of neoadjuvant treatments given in Sweden between 2009 and 2020.

Table 3

pCR rates for different types of neoadjuvant treatment for time periods 2009–2014 and 2015–2020.

TYPE OF TREATMENT		2009–2014	2015–2020	P-VALUE
SCRT + immediate surgery	Total	2759	1522	0.294
	pCR	20 (0.7%)	7 (0.5%)	
SCRT + delayed surgery	Total	883	1307	0.361
	pCR	54 (6.1%)	68 (5.2%)	
SCRT + chemotherapy	Total	182	681	<0.001
	pCR	25 (13.7%)	47 (6.9%)	
CRT	Total	1229	916	0.858
	pCR	102 (8.3%)	78 (8.5%)	

Table 4

pCR rates for all regions in Sweden for time periods 2009–2014 and 2015–2020.

REGION		2009–2014	2015–2020	P-VALUE
A	Total	1319	1166	0.094
	pCR	76 (5.8%)	50 (4.3%)	
B	Total	511	431	0.006*
	pCR	12 (2.3%)	25 (5.8%)	
C	Total	998	949	0.329
	pCR	28 (2.8%)	34 (3.6%)	
D	Total	1005	944	0.398
	pCR	53 (5.3%)	42 (4.4%)	
E	Total	555	563	0.019*
	pCR	13 (2.3%)	28 (5.0%)	
F	Total	944	938	0.734
	pCR	19 (2.0%)	21 (2.2%)	

*For details on type of neoadjuvant treatment see Appendix.

also on a national level [4,13,15,19]. Although the majority of Swedish patients with a cCR are registered in the national WoW study (as recommended in the national guidelines), the “true” cCR rate, and thus overall CR rate, is probably slightly higher considering a small number of patients was already introduced to a W&W policy before 2017 [12]. The increasing proportion of ‘other’ types of neoadjuvant treatment in the public SCRCR data is not fully understood, and seems to be more prominent in some regions than others. Although this makes comparisons between regions more difficult, as well as the comparisons between different neoadjuvant regimens difficult, it does not affect the reported nationwide proportions of pCR and cCR.

It is noticeable that pCR rates for specific neoadjuvant regimens in

the pre-W&W time period (i.e. 2009-2014) in the present study are lower than reported percentages in clinical trials. The reported pCR rates of 10.4% and 28% in the Stockholm III trial and RAPIDO trial, respectively, are almost double of what was found in the corresponding categories on a nationwide level [4,15]. Moreover, a recent meta-analysis reported a pooled pCR prevalence of 14.9% (range 4.2%–21.3%) after CRT versus 8.3% in the present study [20]. To a certain extent this could be explained by the fact this is real-world data and includes all patients compared to randomized trials. However, a nationwide study from the Netherlands in the same time period also reported a pCR rate of 16.2% after CRT [21]. Although the Dutch pCR rate after SCRT+delayed surgery was very similar to our data, their study only included patients with stage III rectal cancer and thus should perhaps have lower pCR rates considering they included relatively more advanced tumours. In Sweden it is standard of care for patients with stage I disease to receive SCRT when a distal tumour reaches the anal canal. This presumably also explains the relatively high rate of APR surgeries in this patient cohort. The variations in pCR rates could to some extent be attributed to differences in patient- and tumour characteristics, but also time interval until surgery. For example, the waiting period of the Stockholm III trial was 4–8 weeks while the national guideline now recommends 6–8 weeks² 18.

There are differences between the six Swedish regions in their choice of neoadjuvant regimens. At the end of the studied time period some regions have almost completely abandoned immediate surgery after SCRT, whereas others still applied this in a third of patients. In the regions that abandoned immediate surgery similar high proportions are seen for SCRT+chemotherapy, which could partly be explained by participation in clinical trials. These regions show a high pCR rate in the first half of the time period and decreasing rates in the second half, probably due to early inclusion in the national WoW study. The reason why the pCR rate after CRT does not decrease as much as it does after SCRT+chemotherapy is presumably due to the categorization of only two time periods and the fact that CRT was already largely replaced by SCRT+chemotherapy at the time of the start of the national WoW study. Moreover, CRT is now primarily used for the large, bulky tumours and, although more research is needed, one could hypothesize a smaller chance of complete response.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this nationwide cohort study shows an increase in overall complete response rate over a time period of 12 years which

indicates that the significant changes in neoadjuvant treatment regimens have resulted in more patients responding with complete response. Whether this corresponds to better survival and quality of life remains to be shown. Our data indicate that if the aim is to give patients the opportunity for organ preservation, optimised neoadjuvant therapy including waiting intervals before surgery, systemic chemotherapy and possibly intensified radiotherapy should be accompanied by meticulous clinical re-assessments and an awareness of a possible complete response.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix 1. Yearly stacked cumulative incidence of types of neoadjuvant treatment given per regions in Sweden between 2009 and 2020

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